

A Machine Learning approach to predict brain abnormalities in preterm infants using clinical data

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Abstract. Preterm infants are prone to several neurodevelopmental impairments (NDI). Early and accurate diagnosis could cooperate in the treatment of their clinical manifestations. Clinical data from a cohort of preterm infants from the Hospital Puerta del Mar, Cádiz, Spain was used in this work to perform a classification task to predict abnormal MRI findings using clinical data. In this paper, we describe an approach using Machine Learning models to predict abnormal MRI findings using clinical data collected at the NICU. Results in this analysis indicate that the best model able to predict abnormal MRI findings was K-nearest Neighbor, with a recall of 0.80. This study represents an initial step towards developing a practical and reliable tool for predicting abnormal MRI findings in preterm infants using readily available clinical data from preterm infants.

Keywords: Machine Learning · preterm infants · neuroimaging · MRI.

1 Introduction

Preterm birth is a birth that occurs before 37 weeks of gestation; its global prevalence rate is about 11% [8]. Preterm infants during their stay at the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) can experience neonatal illness and may need intensified support that might lead to affected brain development and consequently develop short and long-term adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes that include motor, cognitive and behavioral impairments [1, 18].

Neurodevelopmental outcomes in preterm infants have been associated with different causes that go from antenatal, perinatal factors and postnatal factors [32]. An early and accurate diagnosis of neurodevelopmental outcomes is key to treat neurodevelopmental outcomes considering that during early development the brain has greater potential towards plasticity [5].

Clinical assessments of preterm infants during their stay at the NICU can go from clinical examination, cranial ultrasound (cUS), electroencephalography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), etc. Cranial ultrasound is one of the most conventional neuroimaging techniques, this method aims to diagnose intracranial lesions such as intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH), cystic periventricular leukomalacia (PVL), ventriculomegaly, and white matter injury [17, 23], using cUS has advantages such as non-invasive technique, low cost and is available at the bedside [23].

MRI is a neuroimaging technique that captures a detailed image of the brain able to detect in most cases white matter injury, a better delineation of deep structure and cortical injury [32]. MRI has some advantages over cUS, for example, its higher sensitivity to diagnose white matter injury. However, one of the disadvantages is the expensive equipment, time-consuming, implies transport and sedation of the preterm infant in some cases [3], among other challenges that prevent making MRI a routine test for preterm infants at NICUs, particularly in low and middle-income countries [21, 13].

By taking advantage of non-conventional techniques such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) is possible to analyze large datasets and seek for potential alternatives to assist clinical decision-making. Machine Learning (ML) is a type of AI, that branches into supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. A common type of ML used in medical facilities and health-related studies is supervised learning, which branches into regression, classification and ranking. Supervised learning algorithms learn from labeled samples, where the model learn from these patterns and makes predictions. Moreover, Machine Learning has demonstrated to have a significant impact in medicine and healthcare [22]. The use of AI has become an important tool to improve diagnosis, prediction of risk morbidity [15, 24, 39] and mortality [30, 31, 34] of preterm infants in different diseases and its implementation at hospitals has been growing across time and yet different approaches and scopes need to be considered and evaluated. However, one of the greatest challenges of implementing AI in the medical context is the underrepresented conditions willing to assess. In this sense, it is widely known the imbalanced classes that can be encountered in health facilities, and approaches such as synthetic patient data generation have been currently explored [37].

This current work aims to perform a classification task to predict abnormal MRI using clinical data, to determine the best models that worked in this dataset. Insights made in this work can help in the future to clinicians in terms of decision making of performing MRI in preterm infants. The main contributions of this work are next summarized:

- Employ well-known supervised ML models aiming at accurately predict abnormal MRI using clinical data.
- Analyze the effect on the predictors' performance of SMOTE-NC, which is a well-known technique to deal with data imbalance issues.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the study design, data collection, and feature pre-processing. Then, section 3 explains the methods selected in this research and evaluation strategies data have been considered, including the generation of synthetic data. Section 4 describes and discusses the results that were obtained with the current methods, and discusses the potential applications of this work. Finally, section 5 gives an overview of the conclusions of this study and the projected future work.

2 Dataset

2.1 Study design and participants

Data from preterm infants admitted to the NICU at Hospital Puerta del Mar, Cádiz, Spain was collected from May 2018 to January 2021. The clinical database used in this study includes prenatal, perinatal, and comorbidities records from preterm infants admitted at the NICU. Research and Ethics Committee approval and informed consent of participants were obtained for data acquisition in this research.

The clinical variables from this database include prenatal variables which refer to the mother’s health record before and during pregnancy these include chorioamnionitis, gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, cesarean delivery, IV fertilization, etc. Perinatal variables are the ones in regard to conditions of the preterm infant during the delivery, these include gestational age, sex, Apgar 1 & 5, CRIB Index, intubation, head circumference, small for gestational age, cardiac massage, cardiopulmonary resuscitation, etc. Comorbidities are the acquired medical conditions during the patient’s stay at the NICU, these include invasive candidiasis, bronchopulmonary dysplasia, days of oxygen therapy, mechanical ventilation, etc.

Preterm infants from this cohort had a term-MRI scan which was assessed by neonatologists under an MRI scoring system that evaluates the severity of brain injury in white matter, cerebellum, and cortical and deep gray matter [19]. In this work, we analyzed a dataset of 110 preterm infants where 14 patients obtained a normal diagnosis, while 14 preterm infants were defined with an abnormal MRI according to the clinician’s evaluations using the mentioned MRI scoring system. For the prediction of this score in this current research, we used a dichotomized version of the scoring, meaning that patients who had a score < 8 was considered normal, while > 8 were considered from moderate to severe abnormal term-MRI findings.

2.2 Data curation & pre-processing

A total of 60 variables were considered in this study, where 17 Variables had less than 6% of missing values, in this case, variables with missing values were imputed using two simple methods according to the type of variable. These approaches are simple and fast methods to impute, however, opinions from the

clinicians were considered in order to verify if this imputation might not have an overall effect on results.

- Numerical features: Were imputed using the mean value. This implies replacing the missing values with the mean value of all known values for each feature. Later, normalization was performed on these features, which means that each numerical feature was scaled to the range 0-1. This scaling was made on the training dataset, while the test dataset was fitted based on the training data.
- Categorical features: Were imputed using the most frequent value, which implies replacing missing values with the most frequent value of all known values for each feature. The transformation of these features was performed using dummy variable encoding, which means that each category of the variable will convert into k categories, giving a total of k-1 [7].

3 Methodology & Experimental Settings

3.1 Methods

A set of models were considered for this study, in this case since we aimed to compare the performance of different classification models, we selected Logistic Regression, AdaBoost, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gaussian Naive Bayes, and K-nearest Neighbor.

- Logistic regression: As a form of regression model is able to make a prediction by identifying the relationship between one or multiple features that influence the target feature. The formula goes as:

$$P(x) = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + (\beta_1 X_1))}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + (\beta_1 X_1))} \quad (1)$$

Where β_0 is the intercept and β_1 is the regression coefficient of X

- AdaBoost: A meta-estimator that begins by fitting a classifier on the original dataset, by later fitting additional copies of the classifier on the same dataset, but the weights of instances that were incorrectly classified are adjusted so that subsequent classifiers concentrate more on challenging cases. The formula goes as:

$$F(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

Where H is computed as a weighted majority vote of the weak hypotheses h_t and each hypothesis is designated to weight α_t

- **Decision Tree:** Refers to a model that by learning straightforward decision rules inferred from the properties of the data features, it develops a prediction of the target variable. The model resembles an inverted tree, the base is the root node, intermediate nodes, and leaf nodes. In decision trees, the most common measures are entropy (Equation 3) and the Gini index (Equation 4), which are calculated as:

$$E(S) = - \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \log p_i \quad (3)$$

Where p , is the probability of entropy

$$E(S) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^m p_i^2 \quad (4)$$

Where p_i is the probability of an element being classified into a class.

- **Random Forest:** Fits a number of decision tree to distinct dataset subsamples and average them to increase prediction accuracy, their mistakes average out and have better control over the over-fitting.
- **Gaussian Naive Bayes:** Based on the probabilistic approach and Gaussian distribution. The model classifies by considering that the features have an independent capacity of predicting the target feature and that each feature is likely to be Gaussian. The formula goes as:

$$P(x_i | y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_y^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - \mu_y)^2}{2\pi\sigma_y^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

Where σ_y and μ_y are estimated by maximum likelihood.

- **K-nearest Neighbor:** Model that makes predictions, based on the similarity of the data (e.g. Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, Minkowski distance). In this work, the Euclidean distance was used to fit a KNN model to data according to Equation 6.

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - p_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

3.2 Evaluation strategy

To obtain reliable results we opted to implement the models at 5 cross-validation using train-test splits of 80% and 20% respectively (Fig 1). Data pre-processing and evaluation of models were performed in Python 3.10.6, models were imported from the library scikit-learn 1.2.1. The following performance statistics metrics were calculated:

Fig. 1. K fold cross-validation

- Accuracy: Refers to all the correct predictions that the model obtained, and is calculated by considering all corrected predictions divided by a total number of observations. When dealing with imbalanced datasets this metric can not be considered an absolute metric.

$$accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + FP + TN} \quad (7)$$

- Precision: Indicates the fraction of correct prediction across all positive predictions

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (8)$$

- Recall: Refers to the fraction of correctly classified positive examples across all positive examples.

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (9)$$

- F1 score: Indicates a harmonic mean of precision and recall, being the best value 1 which indicates perfect recall and precision. Represent a very useful metric when assessing imbalanced classification datasets.

$$f1 \text{ score} = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN} \quad (10)$$

- ROC AUC-score: Indicates how well the model is able to separate positive and negative samples. When AUC = 1, it reflects that the model perfectly differentiates between the two classes.

$$AUC = \frac{TP \text{ rate} + TN \text{ rate}}{2} \quad (11)$$

3.3 Dealing with data imbalance issues

Due to the class imbalance that we encounter in our dataset, we performed an oversampling method in our training sets using SMOTE-NC(Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique for Nominal and Continuous). This is a variant of SMOTE, for numerical and categorical features [9]. The SMOTE algorithm works by creating new synthetic data points of the minority class, in this case, preterm infants with abnormal MRI, by interpolating between existing examples. It selects a random example from the minority class and finds its k-nearest neighbors. The algorithm selects one of these neighbors and creates a new example by linearly interpolating between the selected example and the neighbor.

4 Results & Discussion

Models performances for standard and SMOTE prediction are shown in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. In this case, the data used in this work infers that the bests models based on the performance were Logistic Regression and K-nearest Neighbor using SMOTE. The selection of the bests models has been taken depending on the main objective of this research. In this case, we aimed to optimize the recall metric (Fig 2), which measures the proportion of positive examples correctly classified, in this sense, K-nearest Neighbor obtained the best results of recall (0.80), followed by Logistic Regression as well (0.60) (Fig 3).

Moreover, obtained considerable results in the ROC AUC score, a metric that reflects the efficiency of the model to discriminate between positive and negative classes, and given this result (0.69), hence we can consider by consensus of both metrics that this is the best model. KNN has demonstrated better performance among other models in previous studies, denoting the capacity of this model to work in medical predictions[40, 25, 35].

Table 1. Performances of classification algorithms.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	ROC AUC
Logistic Regression	0.88	0.30	0.17	0.21	0.58
AdaBoost	0.85	0.30	0.23	0.26	0.59
Decision Tree	0.79	0.15	0.27	0.19	0.57
Gaussian NB	0.67	0.12	0.30	0.16	0.52
KN Neighbors	0.89	0.40	0.13	0.20	0.57
Random Forest	0.87	0.50	0.07	0.10	0.53

Table 2. Performances of classification algorithms using SMOTE.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	ROC AUC
Logistic Regression	0.90	0.63	0.60	0.53	0.77
AdaBoost	0.83	0.18	0.27	0.21	0.59
Decision Tree	0.82	0.29	0.23	0.23	0.57
Gaussian NB	0.67	0.12	0.30	0.16	0.52
KN Neighbors	0.61	0.22	0.80	0.34	0.69
Random Forest	0.87	0.67	0.17	0.20	0.57

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of best models in predicting positive classes.

In this work, we want to highlight the use of Machine Learning as a complementary tool for the diagnosis of abnormal MRI findings, by using clinical data

acquired during a patient’s stay at the NICU. Advantages can be taken by using Machine Learning for data analysis, due to its ability to manage large datasets and obtain reliable results. The analysis of prenatal, perinatal, and comorbidities factors can provide meaningful insights into potential biomarkers that can be considered in the construction of models that aim to help in the diagnosis of brain injury in preterm infants.

Previous work has found that clinical data correlates to abnormal MRI findings [20, 33]. Providing an approximation of potential clinical biomarkers that can help in prioritizing the preterm infants that should go under more rigorous examination, such as the MRI.

MRI is a highly sensitive diagnostic tool for detecting brain abnormalities in preterm infants [14]. However, performing MRI on all preterm infants can be challenging due to potential adverse events on the patients [29], costly [12], and might require sedation or general anesthesia [16, 10], which carries its own risks. These suggestions do not imply that MRI shouldn’t be a routine method for preterm patients, but non-invasive methods such as (cUS) have been widely evaluated to also become a reliable method in detecting brain injuries in preterm infants[6, 27, 26].

While in some health facilities, MRI could be a recommended test for preterm infants, is currently a challenge for the rest of health facilities, especially in Low-Income-Countries [36, 21, 13]. Providing an emerging tool, that with the help of Machine Learning methods can help to advise which patients need to go under this type of examination.

Diagnostic performance using clinical data has been performed before for predicting NDI, where they have stated that the accuracy of the prediction has been found by using an optimal set of biomarkers compared to isolated individual biomarkers [33, 38]. Identifying those significant prognostic biomarkers can help in constructing models able to predict NDI outcomes and helping clinicians in decision-making and guide towards an early intervention [2, 28, 33, 38]. The intention of this work has been to extrapolate this previous work on earlier steps in the diagnosis of brain injuries in preterm infants.

5 Conclusions & future work

In this work, we offer a novel approach using Machine Learning to predict abnormal MRI findings using clinical data collected at the NICU in a cohort of preterm infants from the Hospital Puerta del Mar in Cádiz, Spain. Specifically, we performed a classification task with 6 different models to predict abnormal MRI findings using clinical data, including prenatal, perinatal, and comorbidities records. Due to the class imbalance encountered in this dataset, an over-sampling method (SMOTE-NC) was applied and compared to the initial prediction.

Our results indicate that the best model for predicting abnormal MRI findings in preterm infants was the K-nearest Neighbor (KNN) algorithm, with the

employment of SMOTE-NC. Further models tested in this work have demonstrated that can have a greater prediction (e.g. Logistic Regression, Random Forest) but in the negative class (normal MRI findings) which in some terms can be useful but not in the scope of this research.

Our work has various limitations such as the size of the dataset, the class imbalance, and the lack of external validation. We expect that in the future this work can be reproduced using a bigger dataset and considering further perinatal and sociodemographic data since they have been correlated for short and long term outcomes in preterm infants in previous studies [4, 11].

Nevertheless, this research can be extended by applying further methods, such as feature importance selection or considering further features that have been associated with abnormal MRI findings. Moreover, considering the small dataset in this research is expected to incorporate more patients in the model and even external cohorts that can help into towards developing an efficient and reliable tool to assist diagnosis.

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